

Optimization Approach for Earth-Termination System for Large-Scale Solar Power Plant with Pre-Determined Air-Termination System

Eduard Shulzhenko ^{1,*}, Kamila Costa ^{2,*}, Michael Rock ^{3,*}

** Group for Lightning and Surge Protection, Technische Universität Ilmenau
Ilmenau, Germany*

¹ eduard.shulzhenko@gmail.com

² kamila.costa@tu-ilmenau.de

³ michael.rock@tu-ilmenau.de

Abstract—This paper presents a new approach for optimizing the external lightning protection system (LPS) for large-scale solar power plants (SPPs). Unlike traditional methods, which treat the design of the air-termination system (ATS) and the earth-termination system (ETS) independently, this approach considers both systems together. Integrating both systems provides greater flexibility, enabling the construction of a more efficient LPS, conserving materials, reducing transient ground potential rise (GPR), and ensuring personal safety. Additionally, this approach addresses current challenges by preventing direct lightning strikes to SPP components (such as PV panels), avoiding shadowing, and not interfering with cleaning robots.

The introduced approach proposes that the design process begins with the ATS. In this way, the ATS establishes fixed injection points for the lightning current within the ETS, allowing the ETS to be designed more effectively around these entry points.

It is well known that to control GPR during a lightning discharge, more earth electrodes should be placed within an impulse-effective area, whose size is defined by the frequency and the soil conductivity. The key question that arises is the configuration or system in which these earth electrodes should be arranged within the discharge area around the entry points to account for proximity effects and the effective length at the relatively high frequencies associated with lightning impulse currents.

Firstly, the computational models are implemented in the XGSLab software to find an optimal earthing electrode arrangement for entry points based on electromagnetic field theory, addressing challenges in managing high-frequency and transient behavior during lightning strikes. Secondly, an investigation is conducted using the Dynamic Electro-Geometrical Model (DEGM) to determine the potential locations of the lightning masts within the observed SPP. These strategically placed masts will be located away from the components of the SPP, thereby protecting sensitive panels and power systems from the direct lightning strikes and reducing induced voltages. The masts can be extended when a thunderstorm approaches to avoid shadowing.

Thus, a newly shaped ETS, based on the location of the lightning masts, is further analyzed in terms of earth resistance, personal safety, and material consumption using XGSLab.

The primary goal of this initial investigation is to provide an alternative approach for designing LPS for SPP that addresses current challenges.

Keywords—lightning protection system, air-termination system, earth-termination system, solar power plant, optimization approach, transient behavior, high-frequency analysis, interception efficiency, ground potential rise

I. INTRODUCTION

Large-scale solar power plants (SPPs), which include both photovoltaic (PV) and concentrated solar power (CSP) systems, are crucial for renewable energy generation. Designing lightning protection system (LPS) for these extensive and complex power plants with sensitive electronics, which will meet all currently existing requirements, could be a challenging task [1][2]. Due to the abundance of sunlight, the efficiency of large-scale SPPs in deserts is high, however the relative high resistivity of the soil in these areas poses one of such challenges. Also there is a correlation between solar radiation, air humidity, and the lightning frequency of lightning. Regions with high solar radiation and air humidity are more susceptible to lightning strikes [3].

Despite the importance of an efficient LPS for the reliability of SPPs, standardization of LPS for solar power systems lacks consideration of transient behavior in large-scale ETS [4]. While standards typically address power frequencies (50 Hz / 60 Hz), they do not adequately cover high-frequency and transient behavior [5][6]. Moreover, it is often desirable to prevent direct lightning strikes on the panels or close to them and other components of the SPP to avoid overvoltages in power and IT systems.

The design of the external LPS typically begins with the design of the ETS. This involves the installation of a grid with mesh size ranging from 20 m × 20 m to 40 m × 40 m [4]. However, to save on materials, the mesh size commonly installed in large-scale plants can be much larger. The ATS is designed independently and implemented in various ways. One method involves using air-termination rods mounted directly on the modules, with the number of rods determined using the rolling sphere method according to IEC 62305-3[7]. This method uses relatively small lightning rods to minimize shadowing effects, requiring placement every 6 m to 8 m along the panels, which could necessitate a large number of rods. A drawback of this method is that even minimal shadowing can significantly reduce the efficiency of the PV panels [4].

Additionally, this setup can interfere with cleaning robots that require unobstructed access to the PV panels.

An alternative method to implement the ATS and avoid the mentioned disadvantages is to use the panels themselves as part of the ATS and down-conductor system. However, both methods—using lightning rods or integrating the panels—have drawbacks. The proximity of lightning rods or the lightning current near or through the panels can induce large charges or steep current impulses, potentially damaging the PV modules or bypass diodes. Additionally, this approach involves constructing a common ETS without considering its impulse performance during lightning strikes, which is crucial in regions with dry soil that can cause high ground potential rise (GPR).

To avoid malfunctions or destruction in sensitive systems of today's SPPs, maintaining sufficient immunity margins against transient electromagnetic disturbances caused by lightning remains an important task. Positioning external LPS components away from the SPP structure to avoid direct lightning strikes offers a good solution. Now, when intercepting direct lightning strikes far from the protected structure, the current should then be distributed into the ground via the ETS within a few to several hundred microseconds. During this short period (corresponding to the rise time of the lightning impulse current), the ETS at the entry point should remain low-impedance to avoid a high GPR.

A suggested approach addresses to these issues and offers a specialized LPS design. This begins with strategically placing lightning masts within the SPP to avoid direct lightning strikes to the components. Once the ATS establishes points where lightning discharges into the ground, the ETS can be designed more effectively around these points. Using numerically designed models in XGSLab [8], the ETS design can be optimized for better high-frequency and transient [10].

II. SOLAR POWER PLANT DESIGN

Solar power plants are complex systems designed to harness energy from the sun and convert it into electricity. They consist of various interconnected components and subsystems working together to generate and distribute renewable energy. The main components of PV SPPs are the solar panels, or photovoltaic modules, while in CSP, they are reflectors (mirrors). The solar panels convert sunlight directly into electricity, whereas CSP plants utilize reflectors to concentrate sunlight onto a receiver. Both PV and CSP systems require mounting structures (frames) to support and optimally position the panels or reflectors for maximum sunlight capture. These systems organize their panels or reflectors into subfields (SF) to efficiently manage the operation of the SPP. These SF are strategically arranged to maximize energy generation [9].

Since the primary focus of this investigation is the performance of the external LPS for large-scale SPPs under different conditions, the overview of the structure is limited to the basic components. From the perspective of the external LPS, the mounting structures, according to the IEC 62305-3 [7][4], must be interconnected and can be used as a natural down-

conductor if they meet the minimum conductance requirements indicated in the standard.

III. EARTH-TERMINATION SYSTEM

Implementing a new LPS approach begins with strategically placing lightning masts within the SPP to avoid direct lightning strikes to its components. Once the ATS establishes points where lightning discharges into the ground, the ETS can be designed more effectively around these points. But before starting with ATS design, this chapter addresses the question of how the earth electrodes around each entry point should be optimally placed to minimize GPR when the steep lightning current passes through.

A. Prerequisites for Optimization

An earth-termination system forms the basis for implementing effective lightning and surge protection measures in any SPP. The IEC 62305-3 [7][4] recommends an earth resistance R_A of less than 10Ω for the ETS. In practice, before the SPP goes into operation, the inspection of the ETS is carried out at power frequency. Due to the large dimensions of SPPs, a substantial amount of earth conductors is buried underground, easily exceeding tens or even hundreds of kilometers in total length. At power frequency, the injected current distributes through the entire ETS evenly, as the effect of inductance at this frequency is almost negligible. This means that the entire length of the earth electrodes effectively participates in conducting the injected current into the ground.

As a result, the entire ETS conducts the current, leading to a very low measured earth resistance R_A . Even in cases with high soil resistivity in the upper soil layer (e.g., $\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$), R_A can be measured below 1Ω . This low power frequency resistance can tempt designers to save costs by further increasing the mesh size of the ETS. Consequently, many existing SPPs exhibit poor ETS design with large mesh sizes, which proves insufficient during lightning discharge events.

An example of a single existing SF with a poor ETS configuration, having a mesh size of $340 \text{ m} \times 150 \text{ m}$, is shown in Fig. 1. The analysis shows the different performance of large-scale ETS at power frequency (Fig. 1 *a*) and during impulse current discharge (Fig. 1 *b*). At 50 Hz, the effective discharge area is larger, spreading through the entire ETS, but significantly reduces at higher frequencies around the injection point. Consequently, the earth resistance R_A of 0.6Ω at 50 Hz is much lower than the peak impulse impedance (Z_{ETS}) of 14Ω at 25 kHz for soil with $\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$.

B. Numerical Optimization

To sufficiently improve the impulse performance of the ETS during a lightning discharge, more earth electrodes should be placed in the narrow impulse effective area around the injection point (Fig. 1 *b*). Earth electrodes located outside this impulse effective area have no effect on the maximum GPR as the current does not reach those distant areas (at least during its initial stage, rise time T_1), unlike at power frequency.

Fig. 1 Surface potential distribution over the ETS for $I_{inj}=100$ kA at a) power frequency and at b) higher frequency (25 kHz) corresponding to the lightning

To achieve sufficient optimization, several steps are considered. The first step is to determine the optimal conductor separation d_{opt} . The second step is to investigate the influence of the number of conductors added in the impulse effective area with the previously defined optimal conductor separation. For this purpose, the analysis focuses on a single SF with a size $500\text{ m} \times 300\text{ m}$. To simplify, the analysis transient behavior of grounding systems is performed in the frequency domain. Examining the highest frequency gives a clear view of early transient response [1][2]. The equivalent frequency f_{eq} of lightning impulse with front time T_1 can be calculated using (1):

$$f_{eq} = \frac{1}{4 \cdot T_1} \quad (1)$$

C. Optimal Conductor Separation

Fig. 2 shows changing of the impulse impedance Z at different frequencies: 50 Hz (power frequency), 250 kHz (first negative short stroke current, $T_1 = 1\ \mu\text{s}$) 1 MHz (subsequent short stroke current, $T_1 = 0.25\ \mu\text{s}$) and 2 MHz (steeper impulses) for different values of conductor separation d and different soil resistivities ($\rho = 100\ \Omega\text{m}$, $\rho = 500\ \Omega\text{m}$ and $\rho = 1000\ \Omega\text{m}$). The mutual impedance due to proximity effect increases with the soil resistivity and decreases with the distance between the electrodes. Thus, as soil resistivity increases, the optimum distance also increases. For instance, at 2 MHz and $\rho = 100\ \Omega\text{m}$, the optimal distance $d(Z_{min}) = d_{opt} \approx 0.3\text{ m}$; for $\rho = 500\ \Omega\text{m}$ it increases to about 0.8 m; and for $\rho = 1000\ \Omega\text{m}$, $d(Z_{min}) \approx 1.5\text{ m}$. This means that in “moist” soil (with relatively low soil resistivity), the earth electrodes should be positioned closer together to effectively reduce the transient GPR compared to “dry” soil. It also means that the impulse effective area in “moist” soil is much narrower than in “dry” soil. Thus, the impulse effective area/length decreases with: i) increasing the equivalent frequency and ii) decreasing the soil resistivity, due to the higher wave attenuation as well as the higher current dispersed in the soil.

The optimal conductor separation is defined by considering the worst-case scenario in terms of the higher earthing impedance for the observed ETS: “dry” soil with $\rho = 1000\ \Omega\text{m}$ at frequency of 2 MHz. This results in an optimal conductor separation range $0.8 < d(Z_{min}) < 1.5\text{ m}$. Therefore, the chosen value is $d_{opt} = 1\text{ m}$. Thus, the optimal conductor separation increases with i) increasing the soil resistivity, which implies higher coupling due to stronger proximity effect, and ii)

decreasing the wave equivalent frequency, i.e. higher effective length or larger effective area.

For comparison, Fig. 3 a) shows the variation in normalized earthing impedance across different soil resistivities at a wave-equivalent frequency of 2 MHz. On the right side of the diagram, the curves maintain a constant value, indicating the range where the effective length of the earth conductor is achieved for the specified frequency. Moving left (as the distance decreases), the impedance drops to its minimum value. However, as conductors come closer, the proximity effect intensifies, causing the impedance to rise again.

Fig. 3 b) demonstrates a different behavior of impedance at power frequency relative to the distance between earth electrodes. In the range where electrodes are very close, the proximity effect is observed again, causing the impedance to increase.

D. Optimal Number of Conductors

Fig. 4 illustrates the influence of the number of earth electrodes on the total earth impedance for various soil resistivities at different frequencies. By adding earth electrodes, separated by d_{opt} from each other, there is a more pronounced reduction in impedance in the beginning of the diagrams, when the number of conductors reaches $n = 2 \dots 3$, especially in soils with higher resistivities $\rho > 500\ \Omega\text{m}$.

Fig. 2 Search for an optimal conductor separation for different soil resistivities and frequencies

Generally, the incremental addition of conductors results in progressively smaller decreases in transient impedance. For $\rho = 500 \Omega\text{m}$, only the addition of the second conductor ($n = 2$) provides an efficient reduction. In contrast, for $\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$, three conductors ($n = 3$) could be used to achieve a sufficient reduction in impedance. Thus, when more than two conductors are added (i.e., $n > 2$), the current distribution becomes less efficient, and the impedance reduction per additional conductor diminishes.

Fig. 3 ETS performance for different soil resistivities at a) 2 MHz and at b) power frequency

Fig. 4 Optimal conductor count for different soil resistivities and frequencies

E. Optimization for subfield

For further investigation, Fig. 5 illustrates four different ETS configurations for a single SF (500 m \times 300 m). Configuration 1 consists of a single earth conductor (ring). Configuration 2 is optimized with the optimal conductor separation and number of conductors previously determined for $\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$ and 2 MHz. Configurations 3 and 4 consider grounding grids with mesh sizes $S=40$ m and $S=20$ m, respectively. Different injection points of lightning current are considered for all configurations: at the edge (Conf. 1-4 (A)) and in the middle of the subfield (Conf. 1-4 (B)). The soil resistivity is $\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$.

The comparative simulation results with different impulse currents are shown in Fig. 6: cases a) and b) for positive First Stroke (pFS, 100 kA), while c) and d) for negative Subsequent Stroke (nSS, 25 kA). As expected, the highest voltages (GPR) occur when the injection point is located at the edge of the ETS, as fewer earth conductors are involved in diverting the lightning current into the ground. For the pFS, the optimized configuration 2 achieves a reduction of about 30% for both edge and middle locations (TABLE I, Conf. 2). The earthing grid with a mesh size of 40 m shows about 20% peak voltage reduction at the edges and about 30% reduction in the middle of the grid (TABLE I, Conf. 3). With a denser mesh of 20 m, the peak voltage reduction is 35% at the edge and about 50% in the middle, indicating a further GPR reduction (TABLE I, Conf. 4).

The performance of the earthing grid for steeper impulses, however, is different. With higher frequency (steeper impulse), the optimal separation between earth electrodes reduces, and the response of the considered earthing grid with a fixed mesh size S worsens (earlier defined $d_{\text{opt}} = 1$ m for $\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$ which is less than conductor spacing $S = 20$ m or 40 m). This is clearly indicated by the simulation results in c) and d) and in TABLE II. The optimized configuration delivers astonishing reduction of GPR by more than 30% (TABLE II Conf. 2, slightly higher than in case of pFS), by consuming less materials. The performance of the considered grounding grids (with $S = 20$ m and 40 m), on the other hand, deteriorates significantly, as the effective area is much smaller for a higher frequency. It achieves a GPR reduction of less than 10% in all observed cases with nSS (TABLE II, Conf. 3 and 4).

Conf.	Injection at the edge (A)	Injection in the middle (B)
1		
2		
3		
4		

Fig. 5 Considered configurations of ETS for observed subfield

Fig. 6 GPR reduction in the injection point at ETS for $\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$ in case of positive first stroke (pFS) and negative subsequent stroke (nSS)

TABLE I PEAK VOLTAGE VALUES (GPR) EVALUATED FOR PFS FOR DIFFERENT INJECTION POINT LOCATIONS

Injection	Configuration							
	1		2		3		4	
	kV	kV	Red. %	kV	Red. %	kV	Red. %	
Edge	1130	774	32	893	21	729	35	
Middle	620	430	31	425	31	323	48	

TABLE II PEAK VOLTAGE VALUES (GPR) EVALUATED FOR NSS FOR DIFFERENT INJECTION POINT LOCATIONS

Injection	Configuration							
	1		2		3		4	
	kV	kV	Red. %	kV	Red. %	kV	Red. %	
Edge	1258	832	34	1178	6	1175	7	
Middle	692	432	38	663	4	622	10	

F. Effective length

The key question in applying this optimization technique is determining the optimal spread of parallel earth electrodes from the injection point to save material and avoid unnecessary excavations. In this case, using the concept of “effective length” can help assess the efficient use of material. The impulse current discharges travel via a limited length of the earth electrode from the injection point due to the inductance of the conductor impeding high-frequency current propagation. For evaluation, formula (2) is used to determine the effective length of a counterpoise wire fed at one end, accounting for the nonlinear effects of soil breakdown around the earth electrodes, based on experimental and numerical results [11]:

$$\ell_{\text{eff}} = \frac{6.528(\rho T_1)^{0.379}}{I_p^{0.097}} \quad (2)$$

where T_1 (front time) in μs , I_p is the peak of the applied impulse current in kA, and ρ is the soil resistivity in Ωm . According to this formula, for “dry” soil ($\rho = 1000 \Omega\text{m}$), 2 MHz, and 25 kA, the effective length is $\ell_{\text{eff}} \approx 30 \text{ m}$. Here a reduction factor of 0.8 for ℓ_{eff} , according to Grcev [12], can be applied, as multiple earth electrode arrangements improve overall the impulse

efficiency, resulting in $\ell'_{\text{eff}} = 0.8 \cdot \ell_{\text{eff}} \approx 25 \text{ m}$. This leads to a shorter arrangement around the injection point, forming a “cross electrode configuration” (Fig. 7, A2). To evaluate its performance, it will be compared with the original arrangement (Fig. 7, A1) and with the configuration without connection to the external grounding system (earth ring electrode, Fig. 7, A3). The simulation is performed for nSS with the injection point in the middle. The results show that the maximal transient GPR at the injection point V_{inj} remains the same for all observed arrangements (Fig. 8, about 450 kV). The large earth ring electrode with a dimension of $500 \text{ m} \times 300 \text{ m}$, which represents the global grid, affects only the tail of the impulse current, as expected (Fig. 8, arrangement A3 vs. A1 & A2). This finding indicates that the optimization conducted is effective primarily for higher frequencies at the rise time of the steep impulse current, as intended. However, connection to the entire ETS (global grid) is still necessary to mitigate the current in its tail, thereby reducing integrated parameters such as charge and energy and also to ensure a personal safety during current faults. Additionally, since the maximal GPR remains the same for the optimized configuration A2, formula (2) from Grcev accurately determines the effective length. Such “cross-electrode configurations” could be used in locations where down-conductors or lightning masts enter the ETS.

Fig. 7 Different ETS configurations for investigating the influence of effective length on maximal GPR

Fig. 8 Investigation of the influence of effective length on maximal GPR with different ETS configurations

IV. PRACTICAL APPLICATION

A practical case study is considered for a single SF in the context of designing an LPS, starting with the air-termination system. Additionally, a major question will be reviewed regarding personal safety: can this LPS design ensure personal safety in the event of a heavy fault current, given that the primary focus of the ETS is to improve its performance during impulse current discharge.

A. Subfield Geometry for Investigation

The considered SF, with a dimensions $500\text{ m} \times 300\text{ m}$, consists of PV panels, each 100 m long, 4.58 m wide, located at an average height of 1.5 m above the ground, with a panel inclination 20° . The distance between the panels is 10 m (Fig. 9). Each panel is supported by a support column, each 3.2 m , which is anchored into the soil at an approximate depth of 0.5 m .

Fig. 9 Selected for investigation, a single SF of $500\text{ m} \times 300\text{ m}$

B. Lightning Protection System Design

The LPS design is starting with ATS – with strategical placement of the lightning mast within the SF. They are placed in a such way between the panels, that they provide the interception efficiency (IE) required for the given lightning protection level (LPL). A possible layout with only lightning masts is shown in Fig. 10, with a calculated total IE of 93.4% , which corresponds to LPL III ($97\% > \text{IE} > 91\%$, [13]). This evaluation was conducted using the Dynamic Electro-Geometrical Model (DEGM) introduced and described in [14]. This ATS design avoids a classical approach with lightning rods (or so-called side rods), located directly on the panels at a distance of $6 - 8\text{ m}$ from each other and with a height of about 0.5 m (Fig. 9)

The calculated interception area of the PV plant is $13,850\text{ m}^2$, and the interception area of the air-termination is approximately $195,900\text{ m}^2$. The number of lightning masts is 72, the size of the area is $129,000\text{ m}^2$, and the total size of all the PV panels is $57,2500\text{ m}^2$. The distribution of the lightning masts determines the design of the ETS. The observed layout results in a mesh size of $60\text{ m} \times 40\text{ m}$. Each crossing point in the earth mesh corresponds to the location of the lightning masts. It is very important to establish a current-carrying connect all superstructures (PV mounting system) to each other and to the ETS.

Fig. 10 LPS layout with telescopic air-termination masts designed to prevent direct lightning strikes (color scale indicates striking distance to PV panels)

C. Investigation with Fault Current

Since the ETS is optimized for lightning currents, the main objective of the simulation model is to verify personal safety in case of fault currents (50 Hz). For this, a numerical model (Fig. 11 (a)) was prepared in XGSLab [8]. The following typical fault current parameters are considered: clearance time $t_f = 0.5\text{ s}$, peak value of short-circuit current $I_{sc} = 3\text{ kA}$, and an extreme case of 10 kA . During the simulation, both step and touch voltages along the entire SF are assessed. During thunderstorms, it is not permitted to enter the solar power plant area, so the further analysis of step and touch voltages during lightning events is omitted.

In the case of $I_{sc} = 3\text{ kA}$ (Fig. 11 (b)), the entire superstructure is within a safe area, meaning both touch and step voltages are below permissible values (according to EN 50522:2022 [15], the permissible touch voltage is 225 V and the permissible step voltage is 3875 V). In the extreme case of 10 kA (Fig. 11 (c)), the touch voltage on some parts exceeds the permissible touch voltages due to the relatively high earthing resistance of the single SF ($R_A \approx 1.2\ \Omega$). Considering that this assessment was based on a single SF and that a solar power plant consists of several such SFs, their combined effect would further reduce the earthing resistance to below $1\ \Omega$ even in “dry” soil conditions and, therefore, the entire superstructure would be in the safe area. Thus, the introduced design of the ETS can ensure personal safety in the solar power plant also under extreme short-circuit conditions, even if the earth conductor is not laid directly under the PV panels but between them, in case when the panels are connected to each other and to the ETS.

D. Evaluation of Material Consumption

The SF requires 72 lightning masts, while the conventional concept needs 2100 lightning rods (the case in Fig. 9 with lightning rods at the distance of 7 m). When analyzing the ETS, the one with a $20\text{ m} \times 20\text{ m}$ mesh size would require approximately $17,600\text{ m}$ (considering a slight distance from the outermost earth ring to the final panels) of copper wire, while a $40\text{ m} \times 40\text{ m}$ mesh size would require about $9,400\text{ m}$. The new concept, with a mesh size of $60\text{ m} \times 37.5\text{ m}$, needs about $6,400\text{ m}$ of wire. With optimized electrodes, in the case of a double configuration (two parallel wires, $n = 2$), additional

5,760 m should be accounted for, resulting in a total material expenditure of approximately 12,000 m. This means that even with the double earth electrode configuration, material savings can be achieved by considering the effective length.

(a) Single SF representation in XGSLab

(b) Evaluated safe areas for the superstructures for $I_{sc} = 3$ kA

(c) Evaluated safe areas for the superstructures for $I_{sc} = 10$ kA

Fig. 11 XGSLab simulation model for a single SF (a) and evaluated safe areas around the PV panels with a reach distance of 1 m to the superstructures with (b) $I_{sc} = 3$ kA and (c) $I_{sc} = 10$ kA (safe areas for step and touch voltages are indicated in green, and safe areas for step voltages only in yellow)

V. CONCLUSIONS

This initial study proposes a new approach for optimizing the lightning protection system (LPS) for large-scale solar power plants (SPPs), encompassing both the air-termination system (ATS) and the earth-termination system (ETS). The design process begins with the ATS, which then guides the ETS design. Using the Dynamic Electro-Geometrical Model (DEGM), optimal locations for lightning masts are determined first. This is followed by analyzing and optimizing the earthing electrode arrangement with help of computational models in XGSLab to improve high-frequency and transient behavior during lightning strikes.

The conventional method of using numerous lightning side rods mounted directly on the PV panels causes shading and

interference with cleaning robots and poses a risk of high induced voltages. An alternative approach employs telescopic air-termination masts strategically placed to prevent direct lightning strikes to the panels and minimize material usage.

Simulations indicate that the new, for high frequency optimized electrode configuration, ensures personal safety by keeping touch and step voltages within permissible limits, even under extreme fault current conditions and could potentially save materials compared to traditional designs.

The introduced layout with the telescopic air-termination masts has the advantage of being extendable when a thunderstorm approaches. In clear weather, they remain retracted, preventing any shadow from being cast on the PV panels. This prevents direct lightning strikes to the panels, as well as side flashes, a risk with the initial layout in which lightning rods are mounted directly onto the PV panels.

It is important to note that this study investigates only one possible ETS configuration, marked as the “cross electrode configuration,” installed at each entering point from the lightning masts to achieve a low transient GPR. Other configurations around the injection point could also be considered (for example to simplify excavation efforts on the site), such as multi-branch configurations with sub-branches etc.

Overall, the proposed optimization method for the LPS, including both ATS and ETS, in SPPs enhances the system's resilience against lightning disturbances, could reduce material consumption in comparison to the grounding grid with narrow mesh size, and ensures compliance with safety standards, thereby could be a first step in offering a practical solution for large-scale solar power installations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shulzhenko E. and Birkel J., “Investigation of Lightning Current Distribution in a Large-Scale Earth-Termination System of Photovoltaic Power Plant,” in *Proc. 34th Int. Conf. on Lightn. Prot. (ICLP)*, Rzeszow, Poland, 2018.
- [2] Shulzhenko E., Hannig M., Puttkammer J., and Brocke R., “Efficiency of the earthing system in a large-scale solar power plant during lightning,” in *Proc. 12th Asia-Pac. Int. Conf. on Lightn. (APL)*, Langkawi, Malaysia, 2023.
- [3] DEHN SE, *Lightning Protection Guide*, 4th updated ed. Neumarkt, Germany, 2018 (in German).
- [4] IEC TR 63227: *Lightning and surge voltage protection for photovoltaic (PV) power supply*, Oct. 2020.
- [5] IEC Std. 2778: *Guide for Solar Power Plant Grounding for Personal Protection*, 2020.
- [6] IEEE Std 80: *Guide for Safety in AC Substation Grounding*, IEEE Power and Energy Society, 2013.
- [7] IEC 62305-3: *Protection against lightning – Part 3: Physical damage to structures and life hazard*, December 2010.
- [8] SINT Srl, XGSLab: Grounding Software and Electromagnetic Analysis Software. Italy: SINT Srl, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.xgslab.com/xgslab/general>
- [9] Mendelsohn M., Lowder T., and Canavan B., “Utility-Scale Concentrating Solar Power and Photovoltaics Projects: A Technology and Market Overview,” National Renewable Energy

- Laboratory (NREL), NREL/TP-6A20-51137, Golden, Colorado, USA, 2012.
- [10] Grcev, L., & Grcevski, N., "Software Techniques for Interactive Optimization of Complex Grounding Arrangements for Protection Against Effects of Lightning," in *Proc. Int. Conf. on Lightn. Prot. (ICLP)*, Birmingham, U.K., 1998, vol. 1, pp. 518-523.
- [11] He J. et al., "Effective Length of Counterpoise Wire Under Lightning Current," *IEEE Trans. on Power Del.*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1585–1591, 2005.
- [12] Grcev L., "Impulse Efficiency of Ground Electrodes," *IEEE Trans. on Power Del.*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2009, pp. 441–451.
- [13] Kern A., Schelthoff C., and Mathieu M., "Calculation of Interception Efficiencies for Mesh-Type Air-Terminations According to IEC 62305-3 Using a Dynamic Electro-Geometrical Model," in *Proc. Int. Conf. on Lightn. Prot. (ICLP)*, Vienna, Austria, 2012.
- [14] Hannig M., Hinrichsen V., Hannig R., and Brocke R., "An Analytical Consideration on the Striking Probability and the Total Amount of Strikes to Simple Structures According to Standardized Regulations," in *Proc. 32th Int. Conf. on Lightn. Prot. (ICLP)*, Shanghai, China, 2014.
- [15] EN 50522: *Earthing of power installations exceeding 1 kV a.c.*, European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC), 2022.